

SCIANCE

D6.1

Project Handbook

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Abstract

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The Project Handbook supports the consortium partners in the effective and efficient management of the activities performed in the framework of SCIANCE project. The Project Handbook covers the project implementation procedures and structures and sets out key responsibilities for the engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and the European Commission. The Project Handbook also explains how the consortium will achieve the project objectives, the oversight by the project management team of the partners' progress on specific tasks, and the timely delivery of project results.

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Approved by	SCIANCE Management Committee		

Terminology / Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	General Assembly
MC	Management Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
RAISE	Resource for AI Science in Europe
SAB	Strategic Advisory Board
WPL	Work Package Leader

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SCIANCE Project

The SCIANCE project is a European coordination initiative establishing the foundations for the Resource for AI Science in Europe (RAISE). The project promotes interdisciplinary collaboration to integrate AI into scientific research by enabling streamlined access to trustworthy data repositories, computing resources, and research infrastructures across Europe. Bringing together leading research infrastructures, scientific organisations, and AI centres of excellence, SCIANCE develops a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) through an iterative co-creation process.

Building on a comprehensive AI-in-science landscape analysis, the SRIA identifies long-term research challenges where AI can accelerate discovery and defines cross-domain AI research and innovation priorities, focusing on open, trustworthy, and frugal AI methods for science. A roadmap for infrastructure upgrades and cooperation mechanisms supports its implementation, translating scientific research and innovation priorities into coordinated action. To consolidate the European AI-in-science ecosystem, SCIANCE pilots the RAISE Secretariat, supported by the RAISE Digital Hub, community-building events at annual AIS Summits, and the RAISE Academy, providing a continuous framework for engagement, capacity building, knowledge sharing, and cross-domain collaborations.

By combining scientific domain expertise with AI research and infrastructure knowledge, SCIANCE delivers robust, evidence-based guidance that is scientifically credible and strategically aligned with European Commission objectives, laying the foundations for future collaborative, AI-enabled science in Europe.

Project Consortium

Consortium			
Name	Short Name	Country	Logo
European Science Foundation	ESF	France	
EGI Foundation	EGI	Netherlands	
OpenAIRE AMKE	OpenAIRE	Greece	
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CNR	Italy	
Euro-BioImaging ERIC	Euro-BioImaging	Finland	
– European Molecular Biology Laboratory (affiliated)	EMBL	Germany	
Constructor University	CU	Germany	
University of Manchester	MU	United-Kingdom	
University of Twente	UT-ITC	Netherlands	
National Institute for Subatomic Physics	Nikhef	Netherlands	
German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence	DFKI	Germany	
HUN-REN Institute for Computer Science and Control	SZTAKI	Hungary	
Big Data Value Association	BDVA	Belgium	

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Project Handbook

The Project Handbook supports the consortium partners in the effective and efficient management of the activities performed in the framework of SCIANCE project. It covers the project implementation procedures and structures and sets out key responsibilities for the engagement and interaction with relevant stakeholders and the European Commission. It explains how the consortium will achieve the project objectives, the oversight by the project management team of the partners' progress on specific tasks, and the timely delivery of project results. The Project Handbook contains all relevant planning information that the consortium partners will use as guidance for scheduling their efforts and delivering their results during the project.

The Project Handbook is a living document, and it will be updated as necessary following any decisions to do so in Project Management Board meetings. These changes will be documented in the section “Revision history”. The next updates will include the assignment of the peer reviewers of each deliverable.

1.2 Relation to Other Project Documents

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Project Handbook is overruled by the Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

1.3 Project Summary

SCIANCE aims to position Europe at the forefront of AI-enabled scientific research by delivering a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, an infrastructure roadmap, and a sustainable cooperation framework that bring together research communities, infrastructures, policymakers, and citizens in a vibrant European AI in Science ecosystem.

The project targets five strategically selected pilot scientific areas that capitalise on Europe's established scientific excellence and leading research infrastructures and present high potential for AI-enabled scientific breakthroughs.

Astronomy & Fundamental Physics (Scientific Coordinators: MU and Nikhef) From cosmology to quantum physics and gravitational waves, these discovery-driven and data-intensive sciences face similar computational challenges: extracting weak signals from massive and multimodal datasets, generating fast simulations, and applying trustworthy inference at scale. With international organisations and infrastructures like CERN, ESA, ESO, SKAO, CTAO and ELT, next-generation observatories (Euclid, LOFAR-2, JWST, SKA) and future flagship facilities in particle and gravitational physics (Einstein Telescope, LISA, CERN HL-LHC), Europe combines extensive data resources with cohesive communities, offering a unique foundation for coordinated AI adoption.

Materials Science (Scientific Coordinator: CU) AI is accelerating discovery, design, and deployment of functional and sustainable alloys, from batteries to semiconductors. Europe leads globally through flagship Centres of Excellence (MaX, NOMAD), ambitious initiatives like BIG-MAP (Battery 2030+), DiMAT and PIONEER. By linking fragmented infrastructures with industrial testbeds to handle multimodal datasets and build transferable AI models across chemical spaces, Europe will enable breakthroughs in energy, electronics, construction, and sustainability.

Earth Sciences (Scientific Coordinator: UT-ITC) AI supports climate modelling, disaster prediction, agriculture, and biodiversity monitoring in a domain driven by massive, heterogeneous datasets. The Copernicus and Destination Earth programmes place Europe as a global leader supported by internationally recognised organisations like EUMETSAT, ECMWF and ESA. By addressing key challenges including model interpretability, robust forecasting, and integration across scales and increasing coordination of its unique infrastructures, Europe can leverage AI-enabled Earth sciences into actionable knowledge for climate neutrality and resilience.

Life Sciences (Scientific Coordinator: Euro-Biolmaging) AI is transforming genomics, biomedicine, biotechnology, and systems biology, driving innovation in drug discovery, diagnostics, precision health, ecological monitoring, and sustainable agriculture. ESFRI Landmarks such as ELIXIR, BBMRI-ERIC, Euro-Biolmaging ERIC or ECRIN ERIC and initiatives linked to the EU Cancer Mission and the European Health Data Space demonstrate Europe's leadership in biomedical research facilitation, clinical research coordination, and health data governance. Coordinated efforts to integrate sensitive multimodal data, ensure interoperability, and embed ethical safeguards will enable AI-driven life sciences to deliver tangible societal, environmental and health benefits.

Social Sciences & Humanities (Scientific Coordinator: CNR-ISTI) AI enables new ways to analyse human behaviour, social structures, and cultural dynamics by combining computational methods with insights from social sciences. Europe is uniquely positioned through infrastructures like CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA, and vibrant communities working on ethics, inclusion, and governance. Through increased interdisciplinary collaborations between data science and social inquiry, Europe can foster responsible innovation that strengthens democratic resilience, social cohesion, and cultural understanding.

1.3.1 Specific Objectives and Achievement Indicators

Specific Objectives	
O#1: MAPPING the European AI in Science Landscape	
Deliver a comprehensive overview of AI use in and for scientific research, combining systematic analyses across five pilot scientific domains with thematic reviews of cross-disciplinary AI innovations. Establish a consolidated mapping of European infrastructures/initiatives and a validated registry of good practices on AI-enabled science.	
5 domain-specific state-of-the-art reviews on AI-enabled science 1 state-of-the-art review on AI for Science research and innovations Interactive directory of >100 European initiatives/infrastructures Public registry of >40 community-validated good practices	
O#2: CO-DEFINING Strategic Research and Innovation Priorities	
Develop a Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for AI in Science on long-term scientific challenges, transversal AI for Science research and innovations and interdisciplinary cooperation priorities, co-created through facilitated thematic expert workshops and broader iterative community consultations.	
5 scientific pilot area workshops (10–15 experts each) producing domain-specific prioritised research challenges 5 transversal AI workshops (40–60 experts), producing cross-domain AI for Science research priorities 1 interdisciplinary workshop (~20 experts) defining interdisciplinary cooperation and model-sharing priorities SRIA validated by >30 stakeholders, aligned with EU policies and regulatory frameworks	
O#3: ASSESSING Research and Innovation Infrastructure Requirements	
Identify gaps in computing, data access, governance, and skills for AI-enabled science. Co-design upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms with European infrastructures and initiatives. Evaluate feasibility through multi-criteria analysis to produce evidence for an implementation roadmap aligned with EU strategic frameworks.	
Gap analysis workshop (15 experts) covering hardware, data, governance, and skills dimensions Co-design infrastructure upgrade scenarios and coordination mechanisms (>25 targeted consultations) Feasibility assessment of infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation frameworks Strategic implementation roadmap endorsed by >20 European stakeholders	
O#4: ENABLING AI in Science Community Building and Sustainability	
Establish the RAISE Secretariat to ensure sustainability and uptake of the project outputs. Pilot Secretariat functions for long-term support of RAISE, including communication, community engagement via the RAISE Digital Hub and AIS Summit events, and the RAISE Academy.	
RAISE Secretariat established with Terms of Reference and partnerships with >15 stakeholders RAISE Digital Hub launched and reach >10,000 unique visits Events at 3 AIS Summits (AIS26-28) to facilitate community engagement and feedback, and promote outputs 1 RAISE Academy bootcamp piloted with >50 participants >2 joint activities conducted with AI networks of excellence, partnerships, or initiatives	

1.3.2 Key Exploitation Results (KERs)

Key Exploitation Results		
KER	Description	Objectives
[KER#1] AI in Science Evidence Base	Comprehensive knowledge base consolidating AI in Science and AI for Science state-of-the-art research, good practices registry and European infrastructure mapping	O#1, O#2, O#3
[KER#2] AI in Science Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda	Community-validated strategic framework defining long-term research priorities, cross-domain cooperation strategies, and policy recommendations for AI-enabled scientific breakthroughs	O#2, O#1, O#4
[KER#3] Infrastructure Upgrades Roadmap	Evidence-based scenarios for European AI in Science infrastructure development, including feasibility assessments, investment priorities, and implementation pathways for enhanced resource coordination	O#3, O#4
[KER#4] RAISE Supporting Pilot Functions	Operational pilot of RAISE coordination mechanisms including the RAISE Digital Hub platform, AIS Summit events, RAISE Academy capacity building program, and RAISE Secretariat coordination services	O#4, O#2, O#3

1.4 Project Management and Responsibilities

1.4.1 Project Coordinator (PC)

The Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement. The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for collecting, reviewing and submitting information on the progress of the project, reports and deliverables to the European Commission in close collaboration with project partners and the WP leaders.

Project Coordinator		
Name	Organisation	Role
Jonas L'Haridon	ESF	Coordinator, Science Officer
Adam Brandstetter-Kunc	ESF	Science Officer
Stefania Vitale	ESF	Science Officer
Saranya Roger	ESF	Project Administrator
Laurène Bristot	ESF	Project Financial Officer

1.4.2 Project Officer (PO)

Project Officer	
Name	Organisation
Vasiliki Stergiopoulou	Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)

1.4.3 Work Package Leaders (WPL)

Each Work Package has a named WP Leader (WPL) that is the partner in charge of the leadership and coordination of the technical and economic aspects of the WP. This includes responsibility for the preparation of any technical reports, achieving milestones, achieving deliverables and provision of deliverables to the Coordinator on schedule, provision of interim and progress reports to the Coordinator on schedule. Each WP Leader has a Deputy who can take care of the WP matters in the absence of the WPL.

Work Package Leaders and Deputy			
Work Package	Organisation	Leader	Deputy
WP1	SZTAKI	Edina Nemeth	András Benczúr
WP2	DFKI	Andrea Loesch	Tilman Becker, Marlies Thoenissen
WP3	CU	Daria Platonova	Mariia Snigireva
WP4	EGI	Andrea Manzi	Sergio Andreozzi
WP5	ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
WP6-7	ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
WP8-9	EGI	Magdalena Brus	Sergio Andreozzi

1.5 Management Committee (MC)

The Management Committee (MC) is responsible for monitoring and guiding the project actions and ensures that quality of the work and required deliverables are of high level. MC ensures the integration of research efforts, reports monthly on progress, and takes action on issues.

Management Committee			
Role	Organisation	Representative	Deputy
Coordinator	ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
Scientific Coordinators	Euro-Biolmaging	Dorothea Dörr	Beatriz Serrano-Solano
	MU	Anna Scaife	Rebecca Bowler
	UT-ITC	Mariana Belgiu	Raian Vargas Maretto
	CNR	Roberto Trasarti	Marco Braghieri

	CU	Andrey Ustyuzhanin	
	Nikhef	Sascha Caron	
WP1 leader	SZTAKI	Edina Nemeth	András Benczúr
WP2 leader	DFKI	Andrea Loesch	Tilman Becker, Marlies Thoenissen
WP3 leader	CU	Daria Platonova	
WP4 leader	EGI	Andrea Manzi	Sergio Androozzi
WP5 leader	ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
WP6-7 leader	ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
WP6-7 deputy	BDVA	Gabriel González Castañé	Ana Garcia
WP8-9 leader	EGI	Magdalena Brus	Sergio Androozzi
WP8-9 deputy	OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola	Theodora Kavvadia

1.6 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is the ultimate decision-making and conciliation body of the consortium and consists of one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as “Member”). The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise by the General Assembly. The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the General Assembly at least once every twelve (12) months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member.

General Assembly		
Participant	GA Representative	GA Deputy
ESF	Jonas L'Haridon	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc
EGI	Sergio Androozzi	Magdalena Brus
OpenAIRE	Natalia Manola	Eleni Koulocheri
CNR	Roberto Trasarti	Marco Braghieri
Euro-BioImaging	Dorothea Dörr	Beatriz Serrano-Solano
CU	Mariia Snigireva	Alba Balla
MU	Anna Scaife	Rebecca Bowler
UT-ITC	Mariana Belgiu	Raian Vargas Maretto
Nikhef	Sascha Caron	
DFKI	Andrea Loesch	Tilman Becker, Marlies Thoenissen
SZTAKI	Edina Nemeth	András Benczúr
BDVA	Ana Garcia	Gabriel González Castañé

1.7 Strategic Advisory Board (SAB)

The Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) will be appointed and is steered by the General Assembly. The role and responsibilities of the SAB are described in the Strategic Advisory Board Engagement Plan (Deliverable D6.2).

1.8 RAISE Secretariat

The RAISE Secretariat pilot will be hosted by ESF for the duration of the SCIANCE project. The scope and responsibilities of the RAISE Secretariat are described in the RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference (Deliverable D8.2).

1.9 AI in Science Working Groups (AISWG)

The AI in Science Working Groups (AISWG) will be appointed and is steered by the General Assembly. The scope, role and responsibilities of the AISWG are described in the AISWG Terms of Reference (Deliverable D6.3).

2 Project Scope and Work Structure

The SCIANCE work plan is organised into nine interlinked Work Packages (WPs) and structured across three sequential phases to ensure a coherent flow from knowledge consolidation (Phase 1) to co-creation of research and innovation priorities (Phase 2) and strategic integration (Phase 3). WP1–WP5 cover the core scientific and impact-generating activities, while WP6–WP9 provide the cross-cutting framework for coordination, communication, engagement, and sustainability. Figure 3.1a (Gantt) and Figure 3.1b (Pert) illustrate the temporal and structural organisation of the project.

Phase 1 (M1–M10) consolidates knowledge through a comprehensive landscape analysis of AI-enabled science in Europe (WP1), complemented by the set-up of coordination (WP6) and engagement activities (WP8), with the creation of the RAISE Secretariat and the AISWG, the launch of the RAISE Digital Hub and the first AIS Summit. Phase 2 (M8–M20) focuses on co-creating research and innovation priorities (WP2) and co-designing infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms (WP3), supported by continuous coordination (WP6), communication, and community engagement activities (WP8). Interim validation and stakeholder consultations will be ensured through the RAISE Digital Hub (WP8), the second AIS Summit and feedback from the Strategic Advisory Board (SAB). Phase 3 (M19–M30) delivers the Implementation Roadmap (WP4), integrates findings into the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (WP5), and ensures visibility and uptake of the project outputs through dissemination and sustainability activities, including the pilot RAISE Academy organised at the third AIS Summit (WP9), continuing from WP8), and completion of the project (WP7, continuing from WP6).

The project execution is overseen by a Management Board, chaired by the coordinator (ESF), and composed of representatives from each consortium partners. The coordinator is responsible for overall leadership and quality assurance, supported by the Management Board and the Strategic Advisory Board, whose members provide high-level guidance, review strategic deliverables, and ensure alignment with EC and Member State priorities. A clear escalation mechanism guarantees timely conflict resolution, while cross-cutting WPs safeguard continuity, coherence, and sustainability, embedding SCIANCE outputs within the wider European AI in Science ecosystem.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram showing the overall connections between Work Packages.

Project Tasks			
Task #	Task Name	Task Leader	Organisation
T1.1	State of the Art for Scientific Research Using AI	Dorothea Dörr	Euro-Biolmaging
T1.2	State of the Art for AI Fundamental Research and Technologies	Edina Nemeth	SZTAKI
T1.3	Landscape Analysis for European AI Infrastructure and Initiatives	Andrea Loesch	DFKI
T1.4	Identifying and Evolving Good Practices in AI-enabled Science	Daria Platonova	CU
T2.1	Scientific Challenges Priorities	Roberto Trasarti	CNR
T2.2	AI Research Priorities to Support Scientific Processes	Andrea Loesch	DFKI
T2.3	Interdisciplinary Cooperations Priorities	Daria Platonova	CU
T3.1	Expert-informed Gap Analysis for Data Access and Computing Infrastructures	Daria Platonova	CU
T3.2	Co-design Infrastructure Upgrade Scenarios	Andrea Manzi	EGI
T3.3	AI in Science Coordination Mechanisms	Daria Platonova	CU
T4.1	Feasibility Assessment	Andrea Manzi	EGI
T4.2	AI in Science Implementation Roadmap	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T5.1	AI in Science SRIA	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T5.2	Community Feedback and Alignment with EU Strategic Initiatives	Gabriel González Castañé	BDVA
T6-7.1	Project Coordination and Management	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T6-7.2	Advisory Board Setup and Liaison	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T6-7.3	AI in Science Working Groups	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T6-7.4	Ethics, Inclusion, and Data Management	Marco Braghieri	CNR
T8-9.1	Strategic Communication, Dissemination, Narrative Building and RAISE Digital Hub	Magdalena Brus	EGI
T8-9.2	Stakeholder Mapping and Implementation of the Engagement Strategy	Natalia Manola	OpenAIRE
T8-9.3	RAISE Summits & Stakeholder Consultation Tools and Facilitation	Magdalena Brus	EGI
T8-9.4	RAISE Secretariat, Sustainability & Pilot Functions	Jonas L'Haridon	ESF
T9.5	RAISE Academy Bootcamp Pilot	Natalia Manola	OpenAIRE

2.1 Ethical Considerations

Following relevant HE guidelines, SCIANCE has undergone the Ethics Appraisal Procedure. From a procedural point of view, all partners are responsible for the application of ethical requirements in their work and must ensure that all ethics issues related to activities in the grant are addressed in compliance with ethical principles, the applicable international and national law, and the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement. This includes the ethics issues identified during the Appraisal Procedure (Humans, Personal data), and any additional ethics issues that may emerge in the course of the grant.

The Coordinator has the overall responsibility for the ethics management of the project. In the context of the project, Ethics, Inclusion, and Data Management activities will be managed by CNR, and any relevant issues or questions must be reported to the PC and CNR. The Data Management Plan (D6.4) serves to guarantee that the project's research as well as data management is conducted in an ethically sound way. The dedicated section of the DMP on ethical aspects covers ethical consideration for the project allowing to comprehensive overview of potential ethical issues.

3 Project Time Management

3.1 Deliverables Schedule

SCIANCE Deliverables (Ds) are the channels through which project efforts – and the results thereof – are described and reported. Table below summarises the deliverables of the project, their corresponding deadlines, the partners leading them and the peer-review timeline. One partner will be responsible on a voluntary basis to review the deliverables. The detailed procedure for quality review is outline in Section 3.2.

Deliverables					
#	Deliverable title	Lead	Due date	Review date	Reviewer
D1.1	State of the art for scientific research using AI for each pilot scientific area	Euro-Biolmaging	30/09/2026	15/09/2026	MU
D1.2	State of the art for AI research and innovations relevant for scientific research	SZTAKI	30/09/2026	15/09/2026	Euro-Biolmaging
D1.3	AI in Sciences mapping methodology	DFKI	28/02/2026	13/02/2026	SZTAKI
D1.4	Directory of AI in Science infrastructures & initiatives	DFKI	30/09/2026	15/09/2026	OpenAIRE
D1.5	Registry of good practices in AI-enabled Science	CU	30/09/2026	15/09/2026	SZTAKI
D2.1	Long-term scientific research challenges	CNR	31/07/2027	16/07/2027	UT-ITC
D2.2	AI for Science research and innovation priorities	DFKI	31/07/2027	16/07/2027	SZTAKI
D2.3	Interdisciplinary AI cooperation priorities	CU	31/07/2027	16/07/2027	CNR
D3.1	Infrastructure gap analysis	CU	28/02/2027	13/02/2027	EGI
D3.2	Infrastructure upgrade scenarios	EGI	31/07/2027	16/07/2027	Nikhef
D3.3	AI in Science Cooperation framework	CU	31/07/2027	16/07/2027	Euro-Biolmaging
D4.1	Feasibility Assessment Report	EGI	30/11/2027	15/11/2027	CU
D4.2	AI in Science Roadmap	ESF	31/05/2028	16/05/2028	EGI
D5.1	AI in Science SRIA	ESF	31/05/2028	16/05/2028	BDVA
D6.1	Project Handbook	ESF	28/02/2026	13/02/2026	CNR
D6.2	Advisory Board Engagement Plan	ESF	28/02/2026	13/02/2026	DFKI
D6.3	AI in Science Working Groups Terms of Reference	ESF	31/05/2026	16/05/2026	DFKI
D6.4	Data Management Plan	CNR	28/02/2026	13/02/2026	ESF
D6.5	Short Interim Management Report		28/02/2027	13/02/2027	CNR
D7.1	Updated DMP	ESF	31/05/2028	16/05/2028	OpenAIRE
D8.1	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy	EGI	31/05/2026	16/05/2026	ESF
D8.2	RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference	ESF	28/02/2026	13/02/2026	BDVA
D9.1	Sustainability and Exploitation Plan	ESF	31/05/2028	16/05/2028	BDVA
D9.2	RAISE Academy for Strategic Leadership in AI-enabled Science Blueprint	OpenAIRE	31/05/2028	16/05/2028	CU

3.2 Milestone Schedule

Milestones				
#	Milestone name	WP(s)	Date	Means of verification
MS1	RAISE Secretariat and RAISE Digital Hub operational, AI in Science mapping methodology	1-8	28/02/2026	D8.2 and D1.3, public access to the Digital Hub
MS2	AI in Science Working Groups (AISWG) established, CDE strategy, AIS Summit #1 events	6-8	31/05/2026	D6.4 and D8.1, participant lists for AIS Summit #1 events
MS3	AI in Science landscape analysis completed, location and participating AISWG experts identified for consultation workshops	1-2-3	30/09/2026	D1.1, D1.2, D1.4 and D1.5, list of experts invited to participate in workshops
MS4	Consultation workshops completed, infrastructure gap analysis delivered	2-3	28/02/2027	Workshop proceedings and draft reports, D3.1
MS5	Feedback consultation on AI in Science priorities completed, AIS Summit #2 events	2-3-8	31/05/2027	Feedback consultation reports, participant lists for AIS Summit #2
MS6	AI in Science and AI for Science research priorities, infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms defined	2-3	31/07/2027	D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D3.2 and D3.3
MS7	Feasibility assessment completed, draft SRIA and Roadmap circulated for consultation	4-5	30/11/2027	D4.1, launch of feedback consultations for SRIA and Roadmap
MS8	Final AI in Science SRIA and Roadmap published and disseminated at AIS Summit #3 and pilot RAISE Academy bootcamp	5-9	31/05/2028	D4.2, D5.1, D9.1 and D9.2, participant lists for AIS Summit #1

3.3 Gantt chart

4 Project Internal Communication

4.1 Email lists

For consortium related emails, it is important to ensure that all consortium members are included in email communications that concern them. For instance, when a communication for a particular WP task may impact the activities of other tasks (possibly in different WPs), the partners involved in these other tasks should be ‘carbon copied’ in the correspondence. It is recommended to flag on the email body which partner is requested to provide an answer and to define the specific deadline for it.

The project’s mailing list is available on the project SharePoint. Each partner’s team leader is responsible for keeping the project mailing list up to date. All partners listed in the mailing list (except administrative, legal and financial contacts) are also added to the sciance@esf.org email group, which should be used for general project communications.

The use of the “High priority” flag is recommended to be exceptional and only when an urgent response is requested.

Due to the fact that many partners participate in multiple projects, all email correspondence related to this project will be headed with “SCIANCE” in the subject, followed by the WP number and/or a short title giving context of the content: for example, “SCIANCE D6.1 Project Handbook review”. All emails will be in English unless purely bilateral communication is involved.

4.2 Microsoft Teams and SharePoint

The SCIANCE Microsoft Teams and associated SharePoint are the main channel for internal communication, planning, online meetings and managing shared documents. All partner listed in the SCIANCE mailing lists has been invited to join the SCIANCE Teams and SharePoint.

Each work package has its own dedicated channel within the SCIANCE Teams. Discussions and files related to WP activities are located in the channel and associated folder in the SCIANCE SharePoint, to ensure that information is concentrated in one place, and everyone involved has access to the same information.

The Microsoft Planner tool integrated within Teams will be used for assigning and scheduling tasks and organizing work. WPLs will be responsible for updating the tasks updated in the General channel, “SCIANCE Tasks” tab.

4.3 Data Management

The Data Management Plan (DMP, D6.4) is aligned with Horizon Europe requirements. The DMP outlines how research data and metadata will be managed across their full lifecycle, covering organisation, access, sharing, preservation, and deletion, while following FAIR principles and the rule “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.” It will function as a living document, updated regularly and generally made publicly accessible unless confidentiality is required. Although SCIANCE is expected to produce limited data outputs due to its Coordination and Support Action nature, the DMP ensures compliance with GDPR, intellectual property rules, and ethical standards, including careful handling of limited personal data for project activities. In addition, the project may use AI-based tools to support tasks such as summarisation of documents or transcription of meetings and workshops; any such use will follow ethical guidelines, data protection requirements, and transparency principles, ensuring that no sensitive or personal data is processed without appropriate safeguards.

4.4 Meetings

The Coordinator convenes ordinary meetings of the General Assembly at least once every six (6) months as well as extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member.

The Management Committee will hold monthly virtual meetings on the first Thursday of each month.

The SCIANCE project will also organise monthly policy meetings with DG RTD on the first Wednesday of each month.

In addition, each Work Package Leader (WPL) will organise regular meetings to coordinate work package activities and review progress, and record discussion in WP meeting minutes.

4.5 Agenda and Minutes

All meeting agendas and minutes are stored in the relevant channel in the SCIANCE Teams, in the “Meetings” folder.

4.6 EU Funding Acknowledgment and Disclaimer

The EU flag, funding statement and grant number must be displayed in all communication and dissemination activities and in any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major results funded by the grant ([EU guidelines](#)). EU funding must moreover be acknowledged in all types of public outputs, media contacts and other public statements.

The disclaimer and grant agreement number are in templates stored in the SCIANCE SharePoint:

Short version (presentations)

Longer version (for documents and reports)

4.7 SCIANCE Publication Policy

Information planned for publishing must be sent beforehand to the Project Coordinator and approved by the Management Committee and relevant partners. Notice to MC and to relevant Parties must be given at least 15 days before the publication. An exception is made by social media postings, which can be published at the discretion of the account holder.

As set out in the Grant Agreement, beneficiaries must ensure that at the latest at the time of publication, open access is provided via a trusted repository to the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND or equivalent licenses could be applied to long-text formats. In practice, open access can be provided either before or after the publication of the manuscript in institutional repositories or in general-purpose repositories such as ArXiv or EarthArXiv. SCIANCE deliverable and publication should be uploaded on the [SCIANCE Zenodo community](#).

5 Quality Assurance and Risk Management

The PC coordinates the overall quality assurance of the project, encouraging consortium members to adopt appropriate standards, quality principles and procedures, and verifying the application thereof throughout the entire project lifetime. This involves the clear assignment of roles and responsibilities of consortium members in the execution of the project work and outputs. The PC is supported by the Management Committee (PC) and the reviewers in the implementation of the quality assurance process.

The regular project Management Committee meetings assure that the project work and the timely quality delivery of project deliverables are closely monitored.

5.1 Deliverable submission procedure

The SCIANCE project will produce 22 deliverables which will be a major result of the project and a tool to monitor its proper implementation and timely execution (see Table above, Section 3.1).

Each deliverable has a leading author who is responsible for the production of the deliverables according to the deliverable preparation procedure. The lead author is responsible for circulating the Table of Contents (ToC) and assigning contribution responsibilities in due time and to send the final version of the deliverable for review at least 14 days before the deadline. Updates on deliverable developments are made at MC meetings to assure that the whole consortium is kept in the loop from an early stage in a transparent manner, and the risk of irreconcilable views is mitigated.

A peer reviewer is assigned from the consortium members who sends comments at least eight calendar days before the deadline. Seven calendar days before the deadline, all partners will have the possibility to review each deliverable and have a right to comment even if they have not contributed directly to the deliverable (if comments from PRs are not yet received or integrated in the document this is mentioned in the cover e-mail). All parties contributing to a deliverable should carefully consider whether the deliverable is public or restricted in any way. Four calendar days before the deadline, all comments from partners are received. A final version should be ready two days before the deliverable is due for submission to the EC, at which time the lead author will send the final version in electronic format to the PC and the WP Leader. Any change in the deliverable plan must be communicated to the PC in time and submitted and agreed to by the Funding Authority.

The lead author is responsible for assuring that the reviewing process is done in due time. In cases where the deliverable has received unexpectedly copious feedback, authors send the finalized version as soon as feasible to the final review. Authors act in good faith to integrate comments to the best of their ability and provide info to the PRs on how they did so. In turn, PRs commit to constructive engagement to ensure the high quality of deliverables. Should all else fail, the final decision to submit will be responsibility of PC. The role of quality checking of deliverables will be distributed among all the members of the SCIANCE project on a voluntary basis, and coordinated by the PC.

Deliverables that are updated after submission with significant changes (e.g., addition of the chapter, restructuring of the outline, etc) are subject to the same Quality Assurance process within a reasonable timeframe (~7 days) and consortium agreement. Minor revisions can be made with simple consortium decision.

5.2 Project-related risks and mitigation strategy

Risk Management will be continuously monitored by the PC and PO in collaboration with all partners based on the initial identification of the potential risks and means for their mitigation presented in the GA and further listed in this section, which will be updated as relevant.

Critical risks for implementation and mitigation measures		
Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	WP
Low participation in AI in Science Working Groups (AISWGs)	Engage early through personal invitations and consortium networks. Offer flexible participation models (hybrid workshops, virtual consensus meetings, etc.). Monitor participation and adjust AISWG memberships if required.	2-3-6-7
Insufficient community engagement in consultations and workshops	Develop comprehensive stakeholder database and targeted engagement strategies. Co-locate workshops with relevant conferences attended by workshop participants. Leverage consortium networks and existing relationships. Provide incentives such as networking opportunities and early influence on outputs.	2-3-4-5
Fragmented or inconsistent data collection for landscape analysis	Establish agreements with existing mapping initiatives (e.g. AI on Demand, EOSC, AI4Europe). Use standardised data collection protocols and quality assurance. Create multiple data sources and validation mechanisms. Engage national contact points and infrastructure representatives.	1-3
Misalignment between identified SRIA priorities and EU strategic initiatives	Maintain regular communication with the EC and relevant EU bodies and initiatives through the strategic advisory board structure. Conduct early alignment checks with EU strategic documents and initiatives. Organise dedicated consultation sessions with policy stakeholders online and at AIS Summits.	5
AIS Summits not organised by the European Commission	Project engagement activities are aligned with AIS Summits organised annually by the EC and EU Presidency (e.g. AIS25 in November 2025). If a summit is not organised or postponed, contingency measures (dedicated online consultations and policy workshops, adapt activities to AIS Summits format and date) will ensure continuity of stakeholder engagement.	8-9
Rapidly evolving AI landscape making findings obsolete	Implement monitoring and updating mechanisms through the Digital Hub. Focus on fundamental research rather than short-lived technology recommendations. Track emerging developments through partner expertise and networks. Apply a living document approach with post-project updates via the Secretariat.	1-2-5
Insufficient integration between scientific domains and AI communities	Design and facilitate interdisciplinary workshop uniting scientific researchers and AI specialists. Establish cross-domain working groups and collaboration mechanisms. Monitor integration effectiveness and adapt approaches as needed.	2-4
Coordination challenges in multi-partner consortium	Establish clear governance structure with defined roles and responsibilities. Hold regular coordination meetings and monitor progress. Use collaborative project management tools and communication platforms. Create cross-WP liaison mechanisms. Prepare contingency plans for partner changes or issues.	All

5.3 Continuous risk assessment

If any risk arises, partners are recommended to first communicate it to the WP leader, and if needed to the PC. In addition, a dedicated spreadsheet for assessment of the impact of the emergent risk will be prepared and regular calls for follow-up and updates will be established. Furthermore, to help in identification of further risk and help in identifying clear strategies and needs at institutional level a dedicated Risk Workshop will be organised for that purpose.

The risk assessment and mitigation strategy will be regularly reviewed by the Project Coordinator and Management Committee in preparation for periodic reporting.

6 Reporting and Financial Provisions

6.1 Internal Progress Reporting

The day-to-day progress of the project will be presented by the WPLs on a monthly basis at each MC meeting. For this the WPLs are responsible for gathering all information about the technical progress in their WP from the task leaders. The PC will oversee the overall project progress.

For the technical and effort overview of the project progress, the partners are requested to send to the Project Office an interim report on their progress (1 page report) and efforts (estimated PM spent) at fixed intervals – every quarter for technical part and every semester for effort (c.a., CA section 4.5) – to be submitted to the PC and shared internally within 30 days after the end of each internal reporting period. This will allow the PC to follow up the project progress, which will help identification of possible deviations, and will facilitate the respecting of EC reporting process.

Partners are encouraged to keep a record of any attended meetings by keeping the attendance certificate, presentation, speech or abstract. This will serve as proof of outreach activities. In addition, partners should record their participation to events in the SCIANCE Event Overview file, curated by WP8-9.

6.2 Periodic reporting

The project is divided into two periodic reporting periods (RP):

- RP1: M1 – 18, periodic reporting M19 – 20, review meeting M21
- RP2: M19 – M30, periodic reporting M31 – 32, review meeting M33

The PC must submit to the EC a report within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. This report must include a 'periodic technical report'.

Periodic reporting	
Report preparation procedure	Timing
PC provides reporting templates	a month before the start of the review period
Technical report contributions required from partners for PC control	within 30 days after the start of the review period or adapted to closest institutional possibility
Submission to EC by PC	within 60 days after the start of the review period, or as required by EC PO on the basis of set review meeting date
Pre-review meeting & Review meeting	a month before the submission of the periodic reporting.

6.3 Review Meetings

The date of the Review Meetings is defined by the PC and the PO. The PC will define potential dates based on the partners' availabilities and the PO will select one. The MC will be consulted prior to selecting a final date. The presence of at least one representative of each organisation leading a WP is required, whilst the assistance of all the other partners is recommended.

6.4 Payment Arrangements

Financial provisions are described under the Consortium Agreement - Section 7 (Financial provisions). Payments will be made to the PC, who must distribute them between the beneficiaries without unjustified delay, according to:

- the Consortium Plan (see GA - Annex II)
- the approval of reports by the Funding Authority
- the provisions of payment in CA-Section 7.2

7 Budget Allocation

Estimated budget for the action presented in the Table below (ca. Grant Agreement Annex 2), contains the estimated eligible costs broken down by participant and budget category.

Budget Information Summary											
#	Beneficiary	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Maximum Grant
1	ESF	0.00 €	112,770.00 €	8,462.50 €	25,387.50 €	33,850.00 €	93,842.50 €	55,532.50 €	48,192.50 €	24,096.25 €	402,133.75 €
2	EGI	25,000.00 €	0.00 €	88,750.00 €	87,500.00 €	6,250.00 €	8,750.00 €	7,500.00 €	207,250.00 €	116,000.00 €	547,000.00 €
3	OpenAIRE	32,500.00 €	67,500.00 €	18,750.00 €	4,687.50 €	4,687.50 €	7,187.50 €	5,937.50 €	50,000.00 €	60,000.00 €	251,250.00 €
4	CNR	21,506.19 €	52,299.39 €	8,037.01 €	4,018.51 €	4,018.51 €	24,006.18 €	14,719.18 €	2,009.25 €	2,009.25 €	132,623.47 €
5	Euro-Biolmaging	56,250.00 €	0.00 €	11,250.00 €	5,625.00 €	5,625.00 €	4,062.50 €	4,062.50 €	0.00 €	0.00 €	86,875.00 €
5.1	(AE) EMBL	0.00 €	67,193.75 €	0.00 €	0.00 €	0.00 €	4,547.18 €	3,297.19 €	3,297.19 €	3,297.19 €	81,632.50 €
6	CU	71,812.50 €	108,425.00 €	101,237.50 €	3,281.25 €	3,281.25 €	5,781.25 €	4,531.25 €	6,562.50 €	20,937.50 €	325,850.00 €
7	MU	27,533.73 €	46,131.68 €	13,766.86 €	9,429.87 €	9,429.87 €	11,929.87 €	10,679.88 €	4,714.94 €	4,714.94 €	138,331.64 €
8	UT-ITC	41,130.00 €	69,403.13 €	13,511.56 €	7,053.43 €	7,053.43 €	9,553.44 €	8,303.44 €	3,824.38 €	3,824.38 €	163,657.19 €
9	Nikhef	32,500.00 €	66,250.00 €	16,250.00 €	8,125.00 €	8,125.00 €	9,375.00 €	10,625.00 €	4,062.50 €	4,062.50 €	159,375.00 €
10	DFKI	75,812.70 €	144,969.05 €	10,278.63 €	3,535.24 €	3,535.24 €	5,839.94 €	4,589.94 €	4,239.62 €	4,239.62 €	257,039.98 €
11	SZTAKI	74,375.00 €	65,937.50 €	25,625.00 €	3,906.25 €	3,906.25 €	6,406.25 €	5,156.25 €	1,718.75 €	1,718.75 €	188,750.00 €
12	BDVA	21,250.00 €	80,000.00 €	31,875.00 €	21,250.00 €	63,750.00 €	7,812.50 €	6,562.50 €	15,937.50 €	15,937.50 €	264,375.00 €
TOTAL		479,670.12 €	880,879.50 €	347,794.06 €	183,799.55 €	153,512.05 €	199,094.11 €	141,497.13 €	351,809.13 €	260,837.88 €	2,998,893.53 €

Table 1: Estimated budget of the action

8 Summary of Staff Efforts

Table 2: Staff effort per participant

Summary of Staff Efforts										
Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PM
1/ESF	0	6	1	3	4	12	7	8	4	45
2/EGI	2	0	7	7	0.5	0.5	0.5	14	8	39.5
3/OpenAIRE	4	6	2	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	6	6	26
4/CNR	3	7	1	0.5	0.5	3	2	0.25	0.25	17.5
5/Euro-Biolmaging	5	0	1	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	0	0	7.5
6/EMBL	0	5	0	0	0	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	6
7/CU	8	10	11	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	3	35
8/MU	2	4	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	9.5
9/UT-ITC	3	5	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	11.5
10/Nikhef	2	4	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	9.5
11/DFKI	8	12	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	24
12/SZTAKI	9	6	3	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.25	20.5
13/BDVA	2	6	3	2	6	0.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	23
Total Person Months	48	71	33	16.5	15	20	14	32.5	24.5	274.5

9 References

Reference	
GA	SCIANCE Grant Agreement
CA	SCIANCE Consortium Agreement
EU guidelines	Operational guidelines for recipients of EU funding
D6.2	Strategic Advisory Board Engagement Plan
D6.3	RAISE Secretariat Terms of Reference
D8.2	AISWG Terms of Reference